

**ПІДХОДИ ДО ВИЗНАЧЕННЯ ПОНЯТТЯ «РАЦІОНАЛЬНІСТЬ»:
РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦІОНАЛІЗМ VS ЕНАКТИВІЗМ**

**APPROACHES TO THE DEFINITION OF "RATIONALITY":
REPRESENTATIONALISM VS. ENACTIVISM**

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Representationalists like M. Tay and S. Shoemaker adhere to the traditional philosophical view of rationality and distinguish two types — practical and epistemological. An epistemologically rational person is capable of reasoning, reviewing the bases of his reasoning with the advent of new data, and establishing the truth or falsity of their own beliefs. A practically rational person can act reasonably and consistently; however, practical rationality is subordinated to epistemological.

This division is also supported by classical cognitive science: rationality prevails at the level of cognitive abilities, which appear as the operation of mental representations (i.e., propositional knowledge). At the same time, according to this definition, perceptual states are not rational; at the level of perception, there is only the fixation of sensory data ("raw data"). This step is understandable: if we recognized that perception is rational, then all beings who do not know the language, the rules of inference of propositional knowledge — animals, infants, wouldn't be able to perceive (which is not true).

However, if we consider perception irrational and at the same time assume that it plays an epistemological role for higher cognitive levels (data of perceptual states make understanding contentful, according to Kant), then we must find a link that allows these levels to interact. This is exactly what representationalists are incapable of because they attribute a decisive role to epistemological rationality.

To solve the separation of perception and its cognitive inertia, enactivists (A. Noë, K. O'Regan) propose not limiting rationality only to the mode of judgment but

recognizing that rationality as a conceptual understanding is present in all modes of human activity. For example, to demonstrate his rationality, a person can answer the question "what is a dog?" by simply defining that it is a domestic animal, a domesticated wolf, or they can walk the dog, play with it, take care of it. These actions will demonstrate their understanding of the concept of "dog."

As for perception, since enactivists consider it practical knowledge, rationality is realized through implicit practical knowledge of sensorimotor dependencies — i.e., the knowledge that input sensory data changes depending on our body's movements. For example, imagine a plate on the table which looks elliptical from one angle and round from a close-up.

Clearly, this approach is an example of "bottom-up," as opposed to representationalist, which assumes that rational processes are ones of a higher order and occur solely due to the ability of our brain/cognitive system to operate with symbols and interference. Instead, enactivist rationality appears as an emergent property of the organism, which is realized as the ability to overcome the challenges posed by its environment and achieve its goals (S. Hurley). However, such a definition is broad, so we can attribute rationality, for example, to amoebas, which successfully cope with the environment. Therefore, to avoid inflating the notion of rationality, it is attributed exclusively to agents based on the latter's certification of their identity, i.e., attributing specific actions to themselves. However, we face another problem — defining the concept of agency and its connection to self-knowledge. According to the enactivists, it should be realized in activities rather than in the formation of beliefs about their own identity.